

PERCEPTION ON TELEVISION ADVERTISEMENT BY HOME MAKERS' ON THEIR BUYING BEHAVIOR

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Abstract:

Television acts as a compliment to other media of advertising by making the viewers in some way or the other to gain the knowledge about the products by linking TV commercials through other media of communication too. The objective of the study is to identify the impact of socio-economic profile on the home makers' habit of watching television and to know about the perception of home makers on purchase behavior through watching television advertising. Interview schedule has been followed in this study. 237 respondents were taken for this study, using Convenient Sampling Technique. Simple percentage analysis and weighted average ranking techniques were used for the analysis. The findings and suitable suggestions were incorporated for the present study.

Key Words: Television, Advertisement and Buying Behavior

Introduction:

Advertising acts as the best way in communicating the information about the new or existing products in the market and its availability to its customers. It carries the message or the content of what the producer wants to communicate to the public about his / her product. Even though internet starts to emerge slowly in its role of communication, Television advertising takes the highest role in displaying the products of the producers to a large group of people. Television advertising has the benefits of focusing on targeted group of audience, its influence has longevity and stronger impact on the television viewers, as the attractive audio visual combinations generates a positive mood for those products among the audience.

Viewers of television select their own program preferences and most of the programs hold the promotional advertising, helping to seek the viewer's interest towards viewing those advertisements by their emotional, society oriented, ethical and conceptual construct in displaying their products. Usage of television has grown to a large extent. About 95% of the American households have television as per Nielsen report. Television, as it covers a mass group of audience of different age groups and of different geographical locations, posting of ads in television is felt to be cost-effective and attractive too.

Statement of the Problem:

Homemakers play a vital role in home management and in the purchase of product required to their family for a month or as per their requirements. They also find a better and adequate time in watching television than the persons who move out for jobs. So it becomes the need to focus on the role of home makers in making a purchase decision for their family. Though their husbands are the earners, it is in general that homemakers play an important role in decision making on their purchases.

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives framed for the present study:

- ✓ To identify the impact of socio-economic profile on the home makers' habit of watching television.
- ✓ To know about the perception of home makers on purchase behavior through watching television advertising.

Methodology:

The data for the study have been collected from the primary source by using interview schedule. Respondents belonging to Pollachi taluk alone have been selected for the present study.

Sampling Procedure:

Study area covers Pollachi taluk. The areas include Pollachi town and the villages nearby like Kovilpalayam, Unjavelampatti, Samathur and Muthur. A total of 250 home makers are taken for the study and the interview is conducted among the home makers belonging to the above mentioned area using convenient sampling method. Out of 250 home makers, 237 respondents have given the answers for all the questions and hence only 237 are taken for the analysis.

Limitation of the Study:

- ✓ The respondents belonging to the geographical location of Pollachi and few villages near by Pollachi are alone taken for the present study.
- ✓ The respondents are the one who do watch only Tamil channels are considered.
- ✓ Only the home makers are taken into account and not other groups are being considered.

Review of Literature:

Lokesh Sharma et al. (2013) in their report on “ The impact of TV advertisements on buying behavior of Indian Adults: An empirical study” reviewed with objective of knowing the impact that would happen on the part of the consumers in their purchase pattern after they do watch the advertisements on television. A total of 840 respondents were taken for the analysis and T-test and ANOVA had been used for analyzing the data. The study revealed that adults do had a strong belief over the television advertisements and they had been more influenced in buying a product.

Deepak Kumar & Meenu Bansal (2013), studied on “Impact of television advertisements on buying pattern of adolescent”. A total of 250 respondents were taken for the analysis. The objectives were to know the likes and dislikes of children towards TV advertisement, to identify the effect of it in buying the products and to know the buying pattern of the adolescents. It had been concluded that students were to spend a greater time in watching television during the weekends and they got awareness about the products through watching TV ads but they do not like watching them often.

Geeta Sonkusare (2013), reviewed on “Impact of television advertising on buying behavior of women”. A total of 30 respondents were taken for the analysis. The study was carried out with the view to study the impact of television advertising on the buying mode of the women, to know the marketing pattern of FMCG products, and the purchase power and monthly expenditure are being framed. Structured questionnaires were framed and data were collected. Simple percentage analysis had been made for the study and it had been identified that social and personal factors have more influence and women consumers were highly attracted towards the strategies of marketing adopted through television advertising.

Swati Bisht (2013), made an attempt on the topic “Impact of TV advertisement on youth purchase decision Literature Review”. The identifications of various earlier reviews concluded that, celebrity advertisements had less attractions and does not change the buying pattern of the consumers, Teenagers, though in the era of internet, widely gather knowledge about the products through television advertising, advertising targeted on the people’s emotional and emotional advertisements gather more attraction and consumers who were continuously made to view the television ads were automatically being moved to purchase the products they viewed were some of the finding of this literature review study.

Gayatri & Sheweta Gaur (2012), studied on “Impact of television advertisement on teenagers”. The objectives of study were to know about the teenager’s impact on TV advertising and to know on the brand obsession among the teenagers. A total of 100 teenagers were taken for the study and questionnaires were distributed and analyzed using simple percentage technique. It was found that youth have higher impact on watching television advertising and influence while they do shop. They also formed to have greater attraction if an advertisement was made through some popular celebrity.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Socio Economic Profile

Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age		
21-30 years	79	33
31-40 years	62	27
41-50 years	67	28
Above 50 years	29	12
Total	237	100
Area of Residence		
Pollachi	101	43
Villages near by Pollachi	136	57
Total	237	100
Educational Qualification		
Illiterate	13	6
Up to 10 th std	41	17
SSLC	35	15
HSC	20	8
UG	40	17
PG	45	19
Diploma	16	7
Professional	27	11
Total	237	100
Types of Family		
Nuclear	179	76
Joint	58	24

Total	237	100
Numbers of Earning Members		
1-2	166	70
3-4	64	27
5-6	7	3
Total	237	100
Family Income		
Up to Rs.10,000	63	27
Rs.10,001-Rs.25,000	104	44
Rs.25,001-Rs.40,000	46	19
Above Rs.40,000	24	10
Total	237	100
Monthly Savings of Family		
Less than Rs.5,000	107	45
Rs.5,000 - Rs.10,000	95	40
MorethanRs.10,000	35	15
Total	237	100
Monthly Family Expenditure		
Up to Rs.10,000	116	49
Rs.10,001-Rs.20,000	85	36
Above Rs.20,000	36	15
Total	237	100
Schedule		
Morning	16	7
Afternoon	52	22
Evening	61	26
Night times	41	17
Whenever I am free	67	28
Total	237	100
Duration		
Less than 1 hour	38	16
1-2 hours	105	44
3-4 hours	70	30
Above 4 hours	24	10
Total	237	100
Screening of TV Advertising		
Enjoy the ad	86	36
Take up house hold works sometimes	42	18
Swap the channels	66	28
Watch the ads if related to purchase	43	18
Total	237	100
Influencing Factor		
TV advertisement	113	48
Friends/family/relatives	61	26
Used by famous personalities	36	15
Expert advice	27	11
Total	237	100
Remembrance		
Few hours	8	3
One day	61	26
One week	77	33
One month	71	30
More than a months' time	20	8
Total	237	100
Level of Influence		

Highly influenced	44	19
To some extent	136	57
Never influence	57	24
Total	237	100
Decision Maker		
Husband	40	17
Self	88	37
In laws	41	17
Children	31	13
Joint decisions	37	16
Total	237	100

Table 2: Companion in Watching TV

Companion	Always	Sometimes	Never
Husband	60 (25%)	127 (54%)	50 (21%)
Children	91 (39%)	117 (49%)	29 (12%)
In-laws	42 (18%)	99 (42%)	96 (40%)
Friends	55 (23%)	138 (58%)	44 (19%)
Other relatives	53 (22%)	133 (56%)	51 (22%)
Alone	134 (57%)	73 (30%)	30 (13%)

Inferences:

- ✓ The majority 79(33%) of the home makers belong to age group of 21-30 years.
- ✓ The mainstream 136(57%) of the home makers belong to area of residence of villages near by Pollachi.
- ✓ The most part 45(19%) of the home makers belong to educational qualification of post graduation.
- ✓ The mass 179(76%) of the home makers belong to the nuclear type of family.
- ✓ The majority 166(70%) of the home makers belong to the family having numbers of earning members as 1-2.
- ✓ The majority 104(44%) of the home makers belong to family whose family income is between Rs.10,001- Rs. 25,000.
- ✓ The best part 107(45%) of the home makers belong to the family whose savings are of less than Rs.5,000.
- ✓ The larger part 116(49%) of the home makers belong to family whose family expenditure is up to Rs.10,000.
- ✓ The most 67(28%) of the home makers belong to the category of watching television whenever they are free.
- ✓ The common group 105(44%) of the home makers belong to the category of watching television daily for 1-2 hours.
- ✓ The major group 134(57%) of the home makers opted that they do watch television alone always.
- ✓ The majority 138(58%) of the home makers opted that they watch television with their friends sometimes.
- ✓ 96(40%) of the home makers opted the option as never in watching television with their In-laws.
- ✓ The preponderance 86(36%) of the home makers say that they enjoy the ad content displayed in the television screen.
- ✓ The majority 113(48%) of the home makers says that they are influenced to buy new or existing product through television advertisement.
- ✓ The majority 77(33%) of the home makers says that they are able to remember the television advertisement for a week period of time.
- ✓ The majority 136(57%) of the home makers are influenced by the television advertisement to some extent.
- ✓ The majority 88(37%) of the home makers belong to category of making self decision in product purchase for their family.

Nature of Programme Preferences:

Programme	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	Total	Rank
Serials	57	69	33	10	14	7	13	12	22	237	II
News	58	31	63	16	10	12	12	15	20	237	III
Songs	67	66	39	13	12	11	16	7	6	237	I
Movies	13	29	34	47	49	27	20	11	7	237	IV
Live shows	7	9	14	34	31	41	41	38	22	237	VII
Award shows	11	8	13	30	40	39	38	31	27	237	V
Sports	9	10	17	26	20	27	27	46	55	237	VIII

Reality shows	5	8	10	23	27	40	31	45	48	237	IX
Comedy channels	10	7	14	38	34	33	39	32	30	237	VI

Inferences:

From the above table, it is observed that among the various programmes watched by the home makers, the highest preference has been given for watching songs and the next two highest preferences are being given for serials and news events. The fourth rank is being given for movie channels, followed by award shows, comedy events, live shows, sports events and the reality shows. It is being inferred from the ranking table that the home makers prefer to watch songs, serials and news channels and hence it would be a good inference for the advertisers to focus on these channels to make their advertisements for the products relating to the home makers as well as of the household products.

Suggestions:

- ✓ It is suggested as the majority of the home maker belong to the age group of 21-30 years and reside in villages and they belong to nuclear family television plays a vital role and hence the advertisers can promote trendy advertisements based on the villages cultures and advertisements shall be with the theme which gives emotional bondage with their spouses and children, that helps to create a desire in their minds to buy those products.
- ✓ Based on the family income, their savings and expenditure pattern it has been founded that most of the home makers' family are in lower and middle class family. So the advertisement for the products that are aired in television shall be with the vision of bringing out the economy in using that product, hence it would create positive rhythm in the minds of the home makers toward such products.
- ✓ The majority of the respondents' choice of preferences in viewing TV channels programmes were on Songs, Serials, News and Movies and hence the frequency of airing the advertisements and also the advertisements relating to women and home based products can be advertised in the mid of such programmes so that it can capture the minds of such respondents easily.
- ✓ The frequency period of remembering a particular advertisement is found to be as one week and 30, the repetition of the advertisements can be made at regular intervals of time frame to make the respondents to recall the products at the time of making their purchases.

Conclusion:

Television, focused to be a major role player in taking the happenings of the world to every home, equally has a major role in introducing the products available in the market to the consumers. It generates awareness about the products and helps the geographically diversified group of people to equip their knowledge on the availability of the products.

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